

Perspective

Unlocking the value of digitalization for the European energy transition: A typology of innovative business models

Moritz Loock

University of St. Gallen, Institute for Economy and the Environment, Müller-Friedberg-Strasse 6, CH-9000, St. Gallen, Switzerland

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ABSTRACT

Many researchers and practitioners in the energy domain look at business model innovation to find novel ways of creating and capturing value from digital technology. A key concern is to address problems and inefficiencies in the energy transition. In entrepreneurship such inefficiencies are referred to as bottlenecks. However, the profound potential that digital technology and business model innovation have to address bottlenecks in the energy transition is surprisingly under-researched. This paper contributes to this gap. It appears that digital technologies facilitate business model innovation that either tackle bottlenecks of integrating sustainable energy technology into incumbent structures or bottlenecks that relate to the independence of sustainable energy technology from incumbent structures. Further, business model innovation to address these bottlenecks are either incremental or transformative. As a result, digitalization-based business model innovation appears in four types. Each type stimulates novel prescriptions for business model innovation research and practice and the governance of sustainable energy transitions.

1. Introduction

Reviews have mapped the variety and profound importance of business model innovation for energy practice and research [1–3]. More recently there is a strong focus on novel ways to create and capture value from decentral energy production and consumption. Energy research and social sciences puts attention to business model innovation and the emergence of community solar [4], effects of peer-to-peer electricity trading [5] and opportunities to improve governance for energy sharing [6]. Digital technology plays an important role in business model innovation as important initiatives center around platform business models. Such platforms enable novel ways of providing energy [7], and support the development of local and micro power markets [8]. Overall, business model innovation is helpful to “facilitate, configure and broker system innovation” [9]: 1.

Much of the work on business model innovation in the energy sector, builds on broader discussions of business model innovation. Since Morris, Schindehutte, and Allen’s seminal work on entrepreneurial business models [10], knowledge about business models has increased considerably [11–13]. Of particular interest is business model innovation, as in today’s business environment novel business models are needed across industries. Many of the established business models require updating. Based on a review of the major scholarly contributions, business model innovation may be understood as

“designed, novel, and nontrivial changes to the key elements of a firm’s business model and/or the architecture linking these elements” [14]: 216].

However, while business model innovation often links to the exploitation of technological innovation [15,16] and business model innovation is a central process for technology based entrepreneurship [17,18], we have a relatively limited understanding of how digitalization affects business model innovation. E-business in general has long been acknowledged to provide novel opportunities for value creation [19]. It is important to design business models contingent with specific challenges of digital technology, such as addressing resistance to digital platforms with specific relational business models [20]. Recent advancements in digitalization point to even more fundamental consequences for business across industries so that governments, like the German government, formulate action plans for the digitalization of economies [21]. Impactful digital technology like blockchain enable new forms of digital transactions in the financial industry and beyond [22]. Digital technologies are providing novel foundation to the sharing industry and enable novel connections and interactions of different stakeholders [23–25]. Overall, digital platform technologies are providing a broad range of novel opportunities [26] and enable multi-sided markets [27].

Against this backdrop the paper takes a transition perspective [28] to study the role of digitalization on business model innovation in the

E-mail address: Moritz.Loock@unisg.ch.

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European sustainable energy transition. It is important to note that various inefficiencies, which I refer to as bottlenecks, disturb the energy transition. While coping with bottlenecks is an important task in entrepreneurship [29,30], it is of particular interest to understand how the particular bottlenecks in the European energy transition are addressed through digital technology and business model innovation. The analysis here is based on a unique data set of the EMPOWER project (<http://empowerh2020.eu>), a large EU funded innovation project to develop a smart, local energy market design [31,32]. The data – consisting of broad industry data and thirty-one case studies of digitalization-based business model innovations in the European sustainable energy transition – enables to specify a micro-view on the different design elements of digitalization-based business model innovation. From the data analysis a framework emerges, which specifies the outcome of digitalization and leads to four types of business model innovation. The framework provides novel prescriptions for business model innovation theory and practice in the Energy domain. It points to important pathways in creating and capturing sustainable value through digital technology.

2. Definition, data and methodology

2.1. What is digitalization-based business model innovation?

Digitalization-based business model innovation differs from other business model innovation in three important ways. First, business models in e-business have a strong focus on the relationships between a focal firm and its various stakeholders [19]. It has been shown how these relationships and their activity-systems enable novel ways of creating and capturing value. If business model innovation addresses bottlenecks in such activity systems, this provides opportunity to innovate value creation and value capture. Second, digitalization-based business models are often pursuing an asset-light strategy [33]. Thus, digitalization-based business models do not stick with earlier investments or investments at a certain location or industry. In such, digitalization-based business models can be transferred across location and industry. Third, digitalization-based business models are highly scalable. For instance, platform business models have been found to scale much more efficiently compared to traditional business models, as they avoid gatekeepers [26].

Considering these peculiarities digitalization-based business model innovation can be defined along-side three design elements: (1) Digitalization-based business model innovation is centering around a bottleneck and a particular challenge within the activity system of a focal firm and its stakeholders. (2) Digitalization-based business model innovation offers an efficient strategy to address the given bottleneck, and (3) digitalization-based business model innovation is utilizing digital technology for manufacturing the proposed solution.

2.2. Data and methodology

In order to understand the consequences of digitalization on business model innovation in the Energy domain, this paper processes data from a large research and innovation project for “Local electricity retail markets for prosumer smart grid power services” of the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme: “The EMPOWER concept aims to encourage and enable the active participation of citizens that consume and produce energy in the electrical system. It is based on the insight that a significant reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and an increase of energy efficiency require radical changes in the way we produce and consume energy.” (<http://empowerh2020.eu>). Different data sources of the EMPOWER project have been used in the analysis for this paper. Table 1 provides an overview. A central role for the analysis at hand is the EMPOWER business model collection, which can be assessed in the respective technical project reports [31,32].

As a research method, I build on conventional case-study analysis, which is an established practice in energy and social science research [34]. In order to account for the specific contingencies of the European energy transition the case study data is complemented with industry data to reveal the contextual specifics. Some of the current dynamics in the electric energy industry – the emergence of new technology (such as decentralized energy production) and the emergence of new stakeholders (such as private, sustainability-oriented investors) – are similar to the dynamics of other industries, as for instance discussed in the sharing economy [23–25]. But the changes in the energy industry are also specific: For instance, stakeholders in the energy industry are forced to share existing infrastructure, the electric grid and its respective physical requirements [e.g. the maintenance of a stable 50hz power level, see for instance 33].

In this paper a specific focus is given to the analysis of bottlenecks, which are an important element in entrepreneurship [29,30]. Taken together, this enables to identify different types of business models addressing salient bottlenecks in the European energy transition. Developing typologies has a long tradition in the social sciences, and it relates to the managerial practice of business model making [35].

3. Bottlenecks in the sustainable energy transition

One of the most profound dynamics in the European power sector in the recent years, is the increase and diffusion of decentralized energy production capacities (such as bio-gas, wind or solar PV based power generation assets). Fig. 1 depicts how in the largest European power market decentralized power production surpasses the production capacity of all competing power production asset classes. The decentralized production surpassed natural gas fired power plants in 2006. In 2011 decentralized production exceeded the production of nuclear power plants and hard coal fired power plants. Finally, after 2014, decentralized production has started producing more power than the large, incumbent lignite fired power plants. The accommodation of large shares of decentral, renewable energies is an increasingly important topic.

As the sustainability energy transitions progresses, also markets change. An important dynamic appears as incumbents face significant losses in market performance [31,36]. Some of the incumbent problems seem to refer to the increase of renewable energy. A profound example are price peaks during the mid-day, which have been a valuable resource for established utility companies to re-finance their assets. The increasing amount of solar power in Germany – with peak-production mainly in mid-day – leads to considerable drop in the mid-day power prices on the wholesale market, which is at odds with some of the important value-creating strategies of incumbent, large-scale power producers. Fig. 2 depicts the spot prices of EEX – one of the most important power markets in Europe. It shows basically two important effects: First, it shows that the level of the power spot prices have shrunk since 2011. Second, it also shows that mid-day price peaks tend to vanish. For information about details and the reasons for these two effects please see [[37]: 14].

Table 2 provides an overview of potential bottlenecks in the energy industry. Table 2 also points to digitalization-based responses to these bottlenecks. It serves as a list of propositions to guide the following research process.

Many of the bottlenecks fit the specific potential of digital technology in the energy sector. “Digital technology is already an essential element of the energy world, and its relevance will only continue to grow” <https://www.next-kraftwerke.com/virtual-power-plant/energy-network/digital-technology> (accessed 5th, June 2020). While it appears that digitalization overall is an important driver for business model innovation in energy technology entrepreneurship, a more narrow view reveals different bottlenecks that business model innovation with digital technology addresses in a specific way.

Table 1
Data source, type of data, and use in analysis.

Data source	Type of data	Use in analysis
Industry data	<i>Qualitative industry data:</i> Industry reports, expert presentations at workshops, annual reports of European utility companies <i>Quantitative industry data:</i> energy production capacity over time from different technologies such as wind, solar, market and trade volumes	Familiarization with the industry structure and triangulation of findings Assessment of contingencies, in particular the value of flexibility, triangulation of findings
EMPOWER project data	<i>In-depth case analysis:</i> 31 cases <i>EMPOWER project documents</i>	Creation of typology and value creation mechanisms; validation and specification of conceptual framework Familiarization with the EMPOWER concept

3.1. Bottlenecks of digitalization-based independence

Business model innovation in the data-base centers around innovative products and services that provide the opportunity for the self-production and self-consumption of energy. The decrease in unit costs of decentralized energy technology, such as distributed PV, provides an increasing number of households with the opportunity to invest into systems that enable self-production of energy [for more information on the cost developments see, e.g. [37]]. In such, the diffusion of decentralized energy technology has led to a new role on the energy market, that many energy experts refer to as prosumers [8,38]. Prosumers produce and consume energy. An example for prosumers are private households with a photovoltaic system on the rooftop.

An important aspect in this regard is energy autonomy, hence the degree of self-consumption and the dependence to incumbent power supply. Different forms of self-production and self-consumption target energy autonomy at the household level (e.g. based on decentralized batteries as provided by [www.sonnen](http://www.sonnen.de)) or at the community level (e.g. through local energy tariffs such as <http://www.unser-landstrom.de> or <http://www.lettenstrom.ch>).

Digital technology is an important enabler of new services that facilitate management and coordination of decentralized activities. For instance, the business model of Next Kraftwerke sets up a virtual power plant to coordinate distributed bio gas plants <https://www.next-kraftwerke.com/vpp/virtual-power-plant> (accessed 5th, June 2020).

The development of new technology for the management and coordination of decentralized activities lies at the core of many novel business models in the power sector. The coordination efforts are quite challenging as they cover many of the central aspects that are also covered by incumbent business models. For instance, the company Lichtblick has developed the SchwarmDirigent, which is a technology platform that accounts for the different steering needs in a decentralized energy context <https://www.lichtblick.de/schwarmenergie/> (re-accessed 5th, June 2020). SchwarmDirigent provides interrelated

activities such as energy supply, decentral power supply, grid management, forecasting and optimization, plant operation, trade and logistic or customer relationship management. For these activities the platform deals with renewable energy, mobile and stationary storage, combined heat and power units, decentralized loads, power exchange, reserve markets, smart grids, external market partners, household and commercial customers.

3.2. Bottlenecks of digitalization-based integration

The rise of renewable energies provides an important challenge to existing energy systems: wind and solar based power generation is volatile as they are weather dependent. However, wind and solar substitute other power generation assets that have produced stable and well predictable baseloads. While central power plants, can be easily operated, the decentralized production makes, for instance, dispatch and redispatches more challenging. An important aspect in this regard are aspects of physically required system stability (e.g. maintenance of 50 Hz frequency in the grid), which require new ways of matching supply and demand, as the nature of supply changes.

Thus, an important service which many business models in the data-base offer is value creation through flexibility to accommodate large shares of renewable energy. Companies have developed new business models that combine a service (the timing of demand and supply) with valuable assets (e.g. power production plants) or steerable consumer behavior in order to provide flexibility to the electrical grid [33]. They help mitigating some of the challenges that follow from an increasing diffusion of fluctuating wind and solar power generation. Also prosumers can provide flexibility [38]. For instance, prosumers can provide energy storage capacities in stand-alone batteries or within electric vehicles.

Many business models approach flexibility creation on the demand side, for instance offering demand-response programmes. Demand-response aggregators, such as enernoc or Kiwi power operate on the

Fig. 1. Decentralized and centralized power production (pp) in Germany (in bn. kWh), data source: http://www.ag-energiebilanzen.de/index.php?article_id=29&fileName=20160128_brd_stromerzeugung1990-2015.xlsx (retrieved September 9, 2016).

Fig. 2. Spot prices average day for the month of June (Data from the European Energy Exchange).

intersection of the professional energy industry and the demand-side where consumers (either individual households or large commercial energy consumers) have different knowledge about the energy system and its requirements. In such, the technology based integration of demand-side flexibility resources also requires translation and explanations through a central service [33]. For instance, Kiwi power provides demand side response services and advocates, that “Demand Side Response (DSR) is an opportunity for businesses to earn revenue and reduce energy costs by adjusting their electricity consumption for short periods of time”. <https://www.kiwipowered.com/products/demand-side-response> (accessed 5th, June 2020).

On the supply side, the provision of flexibility is also a challenging new service. Whereas most of the central power plants can be scheduled to operate according to desired time-schedules, wind and PV based energy production is dependent on weather. Digitalization enables new ways to mitigate these challenges, e.g. through the aggregation and aggregated steering of decentralized production [8,33]. For instance, virtual power plant operators (e.g. Lichtblick, NextKraftwerke etc.) coordinate distributed generation assets so that they can provide

flexible supply. Storage providers offer flexibility either through serving decentralized prosumers with individual, house-hold level storage systems (e.g. Sonnen) or through decentralized, communities-based storage solutions (e.g. Strombank).

Digitalization enables new opportunity for value creation by integrating decentralized units into the incumbent, centrally dominated system. For example, the German company nextKraftwerke provides services to more efficiently connect decentralized bio-gas power producers to the national and international power markets. For that NextKraftwerke offers a device called next-box, which leaves the company to aggregate decentralized production and optimize decentralized power generation schedules based on different market signals from spot or reserve markets [8: 202].

3.3. Transformative and incremental solutions for bottlenecks

Business model innovation within the sample provides different responses to energy specific bottlenecks: Self-prosumption utilizes digital technology to enable consumers to become also prosumers and

Table 2
Challenges in the sustainable energy transition and digital technology-based opportunities.

Bottlenecks in the energy industry (selection)	Digitalization-based responses	Example
Renewable and non-renewable energy have different technological requirements	Integration of different technologies	Digitalization-based technologies enables new real-time dispatch and re-dispatch activities
Central and decentral approaches of energy generation and distribution have conflicting interests	Connection of decentralized, local markets with central markets	Digitalization-based technologies (e.g. block-chain) enable new physical (through power routers) and economic (through real time sharing and dynamic contracts) connections between local markets and non-local markets
Collaborations among incumbents and new entrants are constrained	Development of platform business models	Digitalization-based technologies enable the integration of multi-sided buyer seller configurations through IT platforms, such as utility-as-a-service
Production and consumption are not efficiently coordinated	Prosumption	Digitalization-based technologies enables new roles, such the integration of power producers and consumers on one roof (e.g. households or SMEs)
Ineffective incentives	Value bundling	Digitalization-based technologies enable the bundling of value for instance through vehicle-to-grid technologies, that allows to sell battery capacity on reserve markets if an EV stands and the energy is not needed for driving
Co-existence of analogical and big data approaches	Provision of new interfaces	Digitalization-based technologies, such as the next-box of NextKraftwerke, provide opportunities to link isolated assets to a network, and for instance aggregate and market decentralized production units as a virtual power plant
Industry convergence	Across-industry standardization	Digitalization-based technologies can facilitate industry convergence, by providing new standards
Dominance of energy experts over laymen is blocking innovation	Democratization and empowerment of salient stakeholders	Projects like open-utility, buzzn or vandebron empower energy laymen and provide new ways of sharing and trading locally produced power beyond incumbent controlled market places
Conflicts between asset-driven and service-driven activities	Value creation with e-business	Digitalization-based technologies enable new ways of value creation, such as through community building, which helps to
Dynamic and homogenous regulation	Provision of modular, adaptive business model building blocks	Digitalization-based technologies enable provision of compatible, modular services, that can be combined towards adaptive business models that fit the distinct local requirements

Table 3
Digitalization based energy business model innovations, Source: EMPOWER D2.2. business model case selection.

Case	Key words	Bottleneck ¹	Response					
			Transformative		Incremental			
			Self-prosumption	Sharing	Platform formation	Aggregation	Management and control	
1	Beegy	Supplier of smart, decentralized energy management systems, system components (e.g. solar PV, batteries, charging stations) and services	X		X			X
2	Brooklyn Microgrid	local, neighborhood-powered grid operating in parallel to the main grid, community microgrid, Peer-to-peer energy market; Blockchain-based platform, ecosystem of LO3 Energy, Transactiv Grid, etc.		X				
3	Buzzn	Peer-to-peer sharing platform, sharing technology, Energy community, electricity pool		X				
4	Caterva	Energy storage, energy storage management and information provider, partners with N-Energie	X		X			X
5	Change38	Renewable, local energy supply, energy savings; Energy application; Peer-to-peer model; supports consumers to choose where their electricity comes from or can sell their own and to control appliances		X				
6	CPower	Demand response, Demand management, Demand management, Optimized energyManagement and control			X			X
7	Cut energy	Aggregation, project management, load-shifting, platform provider					X	X
8	Energy Pool	Consulting services in grid affairs, Energy data management, Network management			X		X	X
9	EnerNOC	Energy procurement, energy Intelligence Software, Demand Response, Control energy usage, Reduce operational costs			X		X	X
10	Exergy Project	Grid computing, Smart Home, Capture and store heat, energy efficiency, SolarRoad ways, LO3 Energy						X
11	Flexitricity	Demand response, Peak demand management, Monetise energy flexibility, Alpiq					X	X
12	GridSense	Energy consumption control, Load balancing, Energy efficiency, Cost efficiency, Alpiq, power frequency monitoring, machine learning					X	X
13	Grid singularity	Blockchain technology, Decentralised energy data exchange platform, Smart grid management, Energy data analysis, energy transactions, Developing countries, Pay-as-you-go solar		X				
14	Power Ledger	Blockchain technology, Automated market, Energy trading, P2P energy trading, Monetise energy surplus, Renewable generating technologies, Energy software		X				
15	Kiwi Grid	Smart grid and smart meter solutions, Energy management, Energy IoT Platform, Optimize energy systems, Sustainable resources, different partnerships			X		X	X
16	Kiwi Power	Demand response, Frequency response, Demand management solutions, Sustainable energy consumption, Imbalances supply and demand, Reduce energy consumption					X	X
17	Letten Strom	Local energy, hydro power, energy tariff that sells from urban production			X			
18	Lichtblick	Virtual power plant for prosumers, Battery storage, Optimize local power stations and storage	X				X	X
19	LO3 Energy	Local energy trading, Distributed energy, Sharing economy, Microgrids, Renewable electrons	X				X	X
20	Localpool	Aggregates power supply, community energy sharing					X	X
21	Mosaic	Crowdfunding platform, Energy solutions provider, focus on solar and clean energy	X				X	X
22	Next Kraftwerke	Virtual power plant, Grid balancing services, flexible energy					X	X
23	Open Utility/Plclo	Online marketplace provider, Peer-to-peer energy matching platform, Energy supply chain, Local generation, Local economyware			X			
24	R&Store	Automated demand response, Cloud-based Demand Side Management, Software platform					X	X
25	SolarCoin	Blockchain, Solar energy, Digital currency, Incentivize solar energy			X			
26	Sonnen	Energy storage and energy community, battery, decentralized energy community, Optimize use of self-generated solar power, SonnenBatterien,	X				X	X
27	Strombank	Decentralized energy, communities-based storage solutions, a bank-like power storing model			X			
28	Tiko	Intelligent storage network, Optimize heating systems, Energy consumption control, Heating system, Energy management, Micro-grid, Utilities, Manufacturers, Innovative business models			X		X	X
29	TransActive Grid	Peer-to-Peer Energy Transaction, Ethereum Blockchain, Distributed Energy Resource Control, Real-time metering, Local energy generation, Decentralized energy trading, Local economy, partner with LO3 Energy		X				
30	Unser Landstrom	Sustainability, Environmental protection, Decentralized energy generation, Energy credits, Local Energy						X
31	Vandebrom	Peer-to-peer sharing platform, Virtual communities, Online marketplace for energy, Clean power, Local energy, Low cost, renewable energy source, Energy source choice					X	

¹ (1) = digitalization-based independence; (2) = digitalization-based integration.

produce and consumer their own energy. Sharing based services use digital technology to exchange surplus energy among prosumers. Platform formation enables to integrate novel services with other already existing services. Management and control builds on digital technology to improve efficiency in existing processes. Table 3 provides examples for each of the different services.

The responses that business model innovation offers to address bottlenecks differ in regard to their relation to the incumbent solutions and market structures. Transformative responses are fundamentally different to incumbent processes and might be able to complement or even substitute incumbents. For instance, self-prosumption and sharing are transformative as they lead to novel energy markets. In contrast, management and control or aggregation provide incremental response and promote smaller changes to incumbent structures.

4. Four types of digitalization-based business model innovation

Depending on the bottlenecks that business model innovation address (integration vs. independence) and depending on the response (transformative vs. incremental) business model innovation from digitalization can be differentiated according to four types (see Table 4).

4.1. Extending value of sustainable energy technology

Value extending business model innovation utilizes digital technology to optimize value creation and capture. Examples are business model innovations of incumbents that seek to add novel services to their portfolio. For instance, intelligent devices like a home energy controller (HEC), which has been tested with Lechwerke in the South-German region of Wertachau, optimizes energy consumption and production in households on a community-level, which facilitates integration in the electrical grid already at the community grid-levels, and thus makes integration efforts more efficient. Such value extending business models are often working towards two different ways of creating and capturing value. On the one side, they are providing novel value propositions to customers (e.g. providing an improved steering of the home energy system). On the other side, such business model innovations add value also on the supply side. For instance, one opportunity to apply the HEC from the incumbent perspective is to utilize its function to improve grid management and be more accurately able to monitor and work around critical situations within the grid (e.g. peak shaving etc.). Often value added in relation to efficiency and lowering costs of operation exceed the value that is generated through providing additional value to customers.

4.2. Empowering sustainable energy technology

Empowering business models are building on digital technology to make weak actors stronger (e.g. through linking, aggregation etc.). Still a central weakness of decentral energy producers and consumers is their small size. For example, the figures for PV installations registered at the Bundesnetzagentur in October 2016 in Germany indicate that out of 4595 PV installations in October 2016, 251 PV installations have an installed power capacity of > 30 kWp (https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/cln_1411/EN/Areas/Energy/Companies/RenewableEnergy/PV_data_tariffs/PV_statistic_node.html (accessed 31.12.2016)). Since 2015 the two largest PV installations in Germany have been installed in January and February 2015 with an installed power capacity of 9'993.96 kWp https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/cln_1411/EN/Areas/Energy/Companies/RenewableEnergy/PV_data_tariffs/PV_statistic_node.html (accessed 31.12.2016). Compared to incumbent power generation facilities even such larger PV installations are comparably small. The Kraftwerksliste in Germany lists power plants, such as the lignite-fired power plant BoA3⁴ in Grevenbroich, Germany, operated by RWE with 1.060 MW (Netto-Nennleistung (elektrische Wirkleistung)) or the nuclear power

Table 4

Four types of business model innovation in the sustainable energy transition that that follow digitalization.

	Incremental response	Transformative response
Integration bottlenecks	Value extension	Disruption
Bottlenecks of independence	Empowering	Market creation

plant Isar 2⁴ with 1.410 MW Netto-Nennleistung (elektrische Wirkleistung) (data from: Energy generation facilities in Germany as of November 16, 2016 https://www.bundesnetzagentur.de/cln_1411/EN/Areas/Energy/Companies/SecurityOfSupply/GeneratingCapacity/PowerPlantList/PubliPowerPlantList_node.html (accessed 31.12.2016)). On the consumption side, demand-shifting potential of single households and their appliances is also limited. The average energy consumption of a household with 4 persons in Germany is 4.200 kWh (<http://www.die-stromsparinitiative.de/stromkosten/stromverbrauch-pro-haushalt/index.html>, accessed 1.1.2017). In contrast, large, industrial energy consumers, such as the German steel production plant LSW require up to 800 GWh power consumption "approx. 1% of the overall consumption in Bavaria" (<http://www.lech-stahlwerke.de/en/company/environment/energy.html>, accessed 5th, June 2020). It appears that larger central entities in the energy sector have higher influences on dynamics in the energy industry, than smaller entities. Besides classic economic views that support the argument of synergies and favour large scale entities (such as transaction cost economics that points to efficiencies of scale), in the energy industry arguments that favour a central and large-scale production and consumption of energy sometimes also refer to arguments from physics, such as thermodynamics. In addition, various aspects of incumbent energy markets define rules that exclude small, decentral stakeholders. For instance, providing control reserves requires prequalification that often excludes single, decentral power producers from direct market access (e.g. <https://www.regelleistung.net/ext/static/prequalification?lang=en>, accessed 5th, June 2020).

Partly as a result from the successful diffusion of renewable energy, partly as a result from the power struggles with incumbents, the diffusion of renewable energy is seeking new governance. Important here are empowering services provided by digitalization-based business model innovations in energy technology entrepreneurship.

Business model innovation leads to novel services to facilitate aggregation and grouping. Business models like the ones of Tiko or Next-Kraftwerke offer such services for aggregation and grouping. As part of a group prosumers form larger networks and consequently have as a network more market power and impact than as individual members. These networks are able and qualify for participation on incumbent markets.

4.3. Disrupting incumbent structures with sustainable energy technology

Disruptive business model innovations use digital technology to update and replace existing business models. In fact, the reference to digitalization from an incumbent perspective is one of the most apparent references in regard to energy innovation. Governments, like the German government, are issuing roadmaps for the digitalization of the energy transition (<http://www.bmwi.de/EN/Topics/Energy/Grids-and-grid-expansion/digitisation-energy-transition.html>), the German energy Agency has been issuing results of a survey among decision-makers in the German energy industry in regard to the role of blockchain in the energy transition [39].

Digital technology provides novel opportunities for business model innovation of existing firms and incumbents are striving to rejuvenate their business models and search for novel opportunities to serve changing energy markets. An example are changes in the structure of incumbents. One of the most widely visible cases has been the split-up

of operations, that E.ON – one of the largest European companies in the energy sector has been performed: “Since January 1, 2016, new E.ON and Uniper have been operating as separate legal entities. From now on E.ON will focus on renewables, energy networks, and customer solutions while Uniper will ensure the security of energy supply through its conventional power generation and global energy trading businesses.” (<http://www.eon.com/en/investors/spin-off-of-uniper-group.html>).

Overall, the dynamics of incumbents facilitate the development of digitalization-based business model innovations in energy technology entrepreneurship.

4.4. Developing novel markets for sustainable energy technology

Business model innovation utilizes digital technology to develop novel markets, roles and services. A profound example are developments of novel market places and the sharing of energy. These places can be virtual communities (e.g. buzzn or vandebron), communities that are defined through hardware-ownership (www.sonnen.de) or distinct geographical places, such as urban neighborhoods (e.g. the Brooklyn Microgrid of LO3Energy (<http://brooklynmicrogrid.com>) or remote communities (e.g. Hvaler in Norway within the EMPOWER project, <http://empowerh2020.eu>). This provides new opportunities for the sharing of power as for decentralized energy producers the incumbent markets to exchange energy (e.g. the EEX) are not accessible, as they do not prequalify or do not meet the minimum supply quantities that are required to access the energy trading.

The novel business models in the data-based leverage technology to set-up new market places, which can be relatively independent from incumbent infrastructure. For instance, vandenbron and buzzn, provide a peer-to-peer sharing platform that allows decentralized energy producers and consumers to share energy. Buzzn connects individuals with different roles in the buzzn community: power contributors (Stromgeber) and power takers (Stromnehmer). Power contributors and individuals with a decentralized power production unit (e.g. combined heat and power station, photovoltaic or wind generation) that produce more energy than they consume. Power takers are individuals that find it important to use decentralized produced power and who know who the producers are (www.buzzn.de). It is remarkable that buzzn creates an own designation of these two roles and avoids the traditional economic designations of consumers and producers.

While technology is an important element for developing new places for sharing, the single concepts also differ in regard to their exposure to technology. While the peer-to-peer platforms buzzn and vandebron apply more traditional sharing technology, the piclo concept (a peer-to-peer energy matching platform for renewables <https://www.openutility.com/product/>) incorporates digital solutions for matching generation and consumption and providing further data visualisations, analytics and control [40]. Other models, such as the Quartier-Strom project, TransActive grid platform or Power Ledger use advanced digital technology, such as block-chain technology (<https://quartier-strom.ch/index.php/en/homepage/>, <http://transactivegrid.net>, <https://powerledger.io>). Such deployment of advanced digital technology enables disintermediation and facilitates novel market places for direct power exchange of decentral producers and prosumers without incumbent intervention.

5. Conclusion

This paper looks at digitalization-based business model innovation in the European sustainable energy transition. It appears that digitalization-based business model innovation evolves along bottlenecks in the Energy transition (digitalization-based integration or digitalization-based independence) and along the response to such bottlenecks (incremental or transformative). As a result, digitalization often leads to four types of business model innovation. Table 5 provides an overview and points to surprising impact on innovation and novel prescriptions

for management.

In addition, these insights provide further implication for how digital technology and business model innovation affect the governance of sustainable energy transitions and the empowerment of prosumers.

5.1. Implications and future work on governance of sustainable energy transitions

The different types of business model innovation from digitalization provide more fine grained insights into the governance of sustainable energy transitions [28]. While business models can improve governance for energy sharing [6], the different types of business model innovation work differently with existing and emerging market participants. Recently, as sustainable transition in the power sector progress (the diffusion of renewable energies for instance in Germany is very successful and power production from decentralized energy technologies has surpassed power production from centralized power generation assets), novel dynamics have been notified such as intensified niche regime battles [36: 904]. It seems on the one hand that incumbents are more capable of defending their positions than initially predicted [41], on the other hand increasing legitimization such as based on progressing cost reductions also are strengthening the deployment of renewable energies. Based on a perspective of sustainability transitions, in which transition is “associated with a transformation of the regime and a particular power struggle between the current regime, upcoming niches and landscape pressures” [42: 545] it becomes evident how important power and politics are. This supports earlier claims that different actors do not have equal power or strength. They have unequal resources (e.g. money, knowledge, tools) and opportunities to realise their purposes and interest, and influence social rules.“ [43: 897]. It appears that politics and coalitions have an important influence on the dynamics of sustainability transitions [44].

Structures and rules for local power markets yet have to be institutionalized to provide strategic guidance for optimal innovation [31,32]. In these situations business model innovation can provide governance and direction [28: 1739]. The paper at hand shows how digitalization-based business model innovation empower new energy producers and consumers through business models.

Business models are innovation devices in technology entrepreneurship [17]. Given the power struggles and different interests between regimes and niches dynamics, such innovation devices are an important tool. The paper at hand shows how digitalization-based business model innovation accommodates and integrates different bottlenecks. For instance, market dynamics (e.g. based on shrinking power prices and flatter power price peaks) force incumbents to develop novel business models. At the same time, accommodation of large shares of renewable energy leaves new entrants to explore opportunities to more efficiently integrate within the incumbent market. Digitalization-based business models can work for both and enable integration, for instance in joint ventures of incumbents and new entrants like within the case of tiko.

Finally, digitalization-based business model innovation enables conflicting learning, even beyond domains. Business model innovation presented in this paper capitalizes learning from other industries. For instance, Transactive Grid or Power Ledger utilize blockchain technology, and thus capitalize digitalization-based learning and make it applicable for innovation in the energy context. Digitalization-based business model innovation retains such learning from others into activities of value creation and capture.

5.2. Implications and future work on the empowerment of prosumers

An important contribution of this paper becomes apparent by looking back at some of the foundational principles of transition scholarship. It is well-known, even since Machiavelli, that there is a training like effect in transitions in such that simple pathways to

Table 5
Surprising impact and novel prescriptions from the four types of digitalization-based business model innovation in the sustainable energy transition.

	Value extending business model innovation	Empowering business model innovation	Disruptive business model innovation	Business model innovation for market creation
Definition	BMI that utilizes digital technology to optimize value creation and capture	BMI that utilizes digital technology to make weak actors stronger (e.g. through linking, aggregation etc.)	BMI that utilizes digital technology to rejuvenate existing business models	BMI that utilizes digital technology to develop novel markets, roles and services
Surprising impact on innovation	Digital technologies for cost reduction are often more impactful than digital technologies for adding value	Through business model innovation digital technologies can alter power and politics	Digital technologies enable to rebuild existing business models in a leaner way	Digital technology provides completely novel opportunities for problem solving
Novel prescriptions	Innovation managers should focus on process efficiency	Innovation managers should exploit political inefficiencies in energy markets	Innovation managers should mitigate existing processes to novel, digital technology	Innovation managers should re-engage in solution search from a digital technology viewpoint

acquire power will most likely lead to struggles in the retention of power, while struggles to acquire power will lead to more simple retention of power. Many of the current forms of energy policy that have been proposed for the governance of sustainability energy seem to be deliberate attempts to simplify the acquisition of power for sustainability innovators: energy policy facilitates entrance and diffusion of a sustainability technology to the market [45], niches protect sustainability initiatives from hostile environments [46,47] and strategic masterminds provide rational intelligence on how to guide transitions and what to do next so that sustainability transitions are effective.

However, the intense power battles at later stages in the energy transition require that new entrants are well-trained in order to be successful in challenging incumbents in the long term. It occurs that eventually alternative forms of empowerment could provide advantages for later-stage transition processes like power retention and extension. The evolutionary struggles on multiple-levels that shape the emergence of digitalization-based business model innovation seems to provide such training effects.

In sustainability energy transitions newcomers are often lacking initial power: they are distributed (e.g. single households, remote farmers, citizen cooperatives that are managed in spare time), not experienced in regard to specifics of incumbent technology, industry specifics and they lack access to salient resources. Digitalization-based business model innovation and the respective empowering services for prosumers provide novel support as decentral energies move from niches to mass-markets. While it has been questioned how technology (e.g. peer-to-peer electricity) is effective in the empowerment of users [5] and what degree of social acceptance local power markets find [8], the paper at hand advocates to study the specific role of business model innovation for the empowerment of energy users and prosumers. Resistance to digitalization can potentially be addressed through relational business models that are eco-system centered and that offer inclusion of various stakeholders [20]. The specific design of such relational business models to further empower prosumers is of growing interest for energy research and practice.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The author declares that he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

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